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Exploring the Impact of Project-Based Learning on Sustainable Development Goals Awareness and University Students' Growth

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Abstract: This study evaluates the impact of an educational intervention strategy – Project-Based Learning (PBL) – designed to enhance university students' knowledge of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), their integration into academic curricula, and their relevance for future professional and personal applications. The research is motivated by the recognised importance of the SDGs in education and the current limited integration and understanding within higher education settings. The study applied a pre-test and post-test experimental design used, involving 199 first-year students from the University of Cordoba (Spain), enrolled in Primary and Early Childhood Education programmes. The intervention comprised PBL activities aimed at increasing knowledge and perceptions of the SDGs. Data were collected using a questionnaire assessing three dimensions: knowledge of the SDGs, the importance of their inclusion in the curriculum, and the perceived relevance of applying SDG principles in professional and personal contexts. The findings indicate that the intervention strategy effectively improved, albeit partially, students' understanding and perception of the SDGs. There was a significant improvement in students' knowledge. However, regarding the perceived importance of integrating the SDGs into their curriculum and the relevance of the SDGs for their future professional and personal lives, no effects were observed. These results underscore the partial efficacy of PBL in promoting sustainability competences and global citizenship among students, suggesting the need to explore other pedagogical methodologies for greater effectiveness. The study advocates the integration of SDGs into higher education curricula to better prepare students for future challenges, emphasising the need for further research to explore the long-term impacts and broader applicability of such educational intervention.

Keywords: Educational intervention strategy, higher education, project-based learning, SDGs, sustainability awareness.

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Introduction

In 2015, the United Nations General Assembly, during its 70th session, adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, a global action plan comprising 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their 169 associated targets (United Nations, 2015). This initiative followed the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), which guided the international development agenda from 2000 to 2015 (Stafford-Smith et al., 2017). The 2030 Agenda was designed to address a range of global challenges, including the eradication of poverty and hunger, the promotion of peace and justice, environmental protection, and combating climate change (Bebbington & Unerman, 2018).

Implementing the SDGs requires a comprehensive action plan involving various stakeholders, administrations, and diverse institutions. Among these, educational institutions play a crucial role, not only through SDG 4 on quality education but also by contributing to the achievement of all other SDGs through educating and raising awareness among future generations. One strategic approach in education is to integrate the SDGs into education programmes. This integration fosters a deep understanding of the interconnectedness of global and local issues (Waters, 2023). Additionally, incorporating the SDGs into academic curricula has a motivational and engagement effect on students (de la Rosa Ruiz et al., 2019).

Various studies have shown that student knowledge of the SDGs is crucial for their effective implementation (Jati et al., 2019; Yuan et al., 2021; Zamora-Polo et al., 2019). However, there is significant variability in how these goals are integrated into different educational contexts. Despite recognising the importance of the SDGs, there is a lack of

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consensus on the best way to incorporate them into the school curriculum. Furthermore, many students have a superficial understanding of the SDGs and their relevance to their future professional training (Leiva-Brondo et al., 2022; Zamora-Polo et al., 2019). Evaluating the impact of the SDGs in education faces methodological challenges, including the implementation of practical and scalable educational interventions.

While studies exist that explore students' perceptions of the SDGs, there is a dearth of research that thoroughly examines the three key dimensions: knowledge of the SDGs, the importance of including them in course content, and the convenience of incorporating them into professional training. Cachero et al. (2023) highlight the need to integrate the SDGs into the educational curriculum for effective implementation. Similarly, Okubo et al. (2021) emphasise the importance of including the SDGs in course content and professional training to promote their effective adoption. Furthermore, Elmassri et al. (2023) demonstrate that students consider the inclusion of the SDGs in course content to be crucial in terms of enhancing their professional training. Finally, Tejedor et al. (2022) and Collazo Expósito and Granados Sánchez (2020) stress the need to integrate the SDGs into higher education and professional training for transformative education. This study is justified by the need to address partial approaches and provide empirical data that can guide future educational interventions and academic policies.

Therefore, this research focuses on evaluating the impact of an educational intervention strategy that applies a project-based learning (PBL) methodology, designed to improve the knowledge and perception of the SDGs among first-year university students in education degrees (Primary Education and Early Childhood Education). Recent studies indicate that integrating sustainability competencies into higher education through active methodologies such as PBL can effectively support sustainable development goals (Birdman et al., 2022). We hypothesised that educational intervention would significantly improve knowledge about the SDGs, increase the perceived importance of including them in subject content, and improve the desirability of their application in their future professional and personal lives. We tested this hypothesis using a pretest-posttest control group design. The results provide an overview of the effectiveness of the intervention and offer valuable recommendations for future implementations in education (e.g., designing more effective educational programmes that integrate the SDGs).

Literature Review

Previous Studies on the Integration of SDGs in Education

Despite the acknowledged relevance of the SDGs in the educational sphere, previous research on their integration into education is limited. The existing literature addresses the evaluation of SDG knowledge but does not focus on how this knowledge translates into the internalisation of values and attitudes and their transfer into specific educational contexts. In this regard, Leal Filho et al. (2018) highlight that, although there is growing interest in the SDGs, many educational institutions have not yet comprehensively incorporated these goals into their curricula, citing obstacles such as a lack of understanding of sustainable development, limited resources, and resistance to change.

Another underexplored aspect in previous studies is the scarcity of sources on specific educational interventions designed to address SDG knowledge, their perceived importance in student curricula, and, finally, the prospect of implementing a future educational programme based on the SDGs for tomorrow's teachers. Sterling et al. (2013) emphasise that although various educational initiatives have been implemented to promote sustainability, there is a lack of empirical evidence demonstrating the impact of these interventions on transforming student attitudes and behaviours.

Since the past decade, the SDGs have been incorporated into various educational contexts. Leal Filho et al. (2016) applied an evaluation tool to measure the integration of sustainability in various universities, focusing on strengths and weaknesses to improve the academic curriculum. The study results confirmed that although there has been some progress in integrating sustainability, significant challenges remain, such as the lack of resources and teacher training.

Addressing these challenges in higher education, Ávila et al. (2017) conducted research through questionnaires and interviews with academics and higher education managers. They concluded that the main barriers to innovation and sustainability are resistance to change, lack of funding, and a lack of empathy towards sustainability.

Despite these challenges, a new institutional dynamic is emerging, or at least attempts to move towards sustainability. Sterling et al. (2013) made a compilation of various university initiatives to address sustainability on their campuses and in their curricula. The study concluded that universities play a crucial role in promoting sustainability, not only academically but also through institutional management. Decisive leadership and collaboration with other institutions are fundamental for the success of these initiatives. In this vein, Laurett et al. (2022) analysed the implementation of a sustainable project in higher education through 18 campus actions, highlighting the importance of higher education for sustainability and its influence on other institutions by serving as a model.

From an educational perspective, some studies have analysed the competencies that universities should foster to prepare students for a sustainable future. Rieckmann (2012) identified systemic thinking, foresight, and the ability to manage uncertainty as key elements to be incorporated into curricula through active learning methodologies. Regarding the development of pedagogical competencies, the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture's EDUCase Platform initiative

is notable (EDUCase Platform, 2024). It brings together various higher education institutions to promote sustainable development and innovation, encouraging intercultural strategies on global responsibility and participatory approaches to sustainable development.

Another aspect to consider in this literature review is the evaluation of sustainability competencies and the tools used (Brundiens & Wiek, 2011). Redman et al. (2021) reviewed different tools for assessing sustainability competencies, using various methodologies applied in different educational contexts. The authors concluded that, depending on the tool used, some emphasise theoretical knowledge while others focus on skills and attitudes. Furthermore, they highlighted the importance of integrating the evaluation of sustainability competencies into the curriculum, which is crucial for students to acquire the necessary skills to solve global problems.

Despite the surge in integrating SDGs into higher education curricula, continued research in this area is necessary. A bibliographic review conducted on 114 sources from 2015 to 2021 revealed that although the number of publications on SDGs and Education – also including higher education – has increased in recent years, citations remain low, and more research is needed (Ferrer-Estévez & Chalmeta, 2021). Additionally, the results highlighted the need to develop a framework guide to route institutions towards achieving the SDGs.

Benefits of SDG Education for Students

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) empowers students to make informed and responsible decisions (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2023). This document emphasises the need for ESD to equip students with the knowledge, attitudes, and values that promote social justice.

Previous literature has found studies that analyse the potential benefits of integrating SDGs into the academic curriculum. Dimaala (2023) argued that integrating SDGs into the educational curriculum promotes critical thinking and social responsibility. Specifically, the author conducted an analysis, concluding that such integration prepares students as change agents and fosters a holistic understanding of global challenges.

Another line of benefits is the preparation for professional and personal life. Kioupi and Voulvoulis (2019) stated that education plays a critical role in building capacities for sustainability, providing significant benefits in formal educational settings, aligning educational strategies with the vision of sustainability, and overcoming structural and cultural barriers. Similarly, Radha and Arumugam (2023) suggested that institutions implementing the SDGs could see improvements in student engagement, education quality, and social impact. However, challenges such as resistance to change and the need for adequate teacher training were also mentioned.

Knowledge of the SDGs and Methods to Improve It

The UN General Assembly established the 17 SDGs in 2015 to address various challenges related to poverty, hunger, health, education, gender equality, clean water, sanitation, energy, and other issues (United Nations, 2015). One of the dimensions of the study carried out is knowledge of the SDGs. This element includes several key components: a general understanding of the SDGs and their history, specific knowledge of each of the 17 goals, and the thematic areas they cover (Ávila et al., 2017). In addition, it is essential to understand the interrelationships between the SDGs and implementation strategies, as well as the actors involved (Laurett et al., 2022; Sterling et al., 2013). In addition, fostering key competencies such as systemic thinking, anticipatory thinking, and critical thinking is crucial for understanding the interrelationships between the SDGs and implementation strategies, as well as the actors involved Rieckmann (2012). Finally, challenges and opportunities for action should be considered, integrating cultural perspectives and encouraging citizen participation (EDUCase Platform, 2024).

Furthermore, there is a need to conduct a review of methodologies that have proven to be effective in improving knowledge of the SDGs. In this regard, previous studies have shown that PBL methodologies can enhance understanding of the SDGs while engaging students (Chen et al., 2022). PBL is an active educational approach in which students acquire knowledge and skills by working over an extended period to investigate and respond to a complex question, problem, or challenge (Žerovnik & Nančovska Šerbec, 2021). This methodology is characterised as active and learner-centred, promoting learning through the completion of meaningful and authentic projects. The learner-centred approach is fundamental, as students take an active role in their own learning, engaging in projects that are relevant and interesting to them. Additionally, these projects are carried out in groups, encouraging teamwork and collaborative skills (Balleisen et al., 2024). During the development of the projects, students must research, analyse and synthesise information to solve the problem posed. The projects culminate in tangible end products that students present and share, either as presentations, reports, or videos, among other formats. Finally, students reflect on what they have learned and on the learning process, identifying their strengths and areas for improvement.

Moreover, the reviewed sources indicate that collaborative learning accompanied by an interdisciplinary approach helps students understand the interconnection of sustainability issues while promoting the development of critical and reflective skills (Fukuda-Parr, 2022; Wiek et al., 2011). Other studies have advanced that a collaborative and interdisciplinary approach in higher education can address issues of sustainability, citizenship and science (Wisely et al.,

2010). Indeed, interdisciplinary synergies are crucial for addressing sustainability challenges, providing students with a holistic understanding of problems (Das et al., 2024).

Another methodological aspect to consider is the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). Regarding the importance of ICT in implementing the SDGs in the educational context, the United Nations (United Nations, 2017) highlighted the importance of investing in ICT access and quality education to promote lasting peace. Such tools significantly improve access to relevant and updated information about the SDGs, facilitating more dynamic and interactive learning. Olojo (2021) stated that integrating ICT in classrooms facilitates innovative methodologies, leading to greater student participation and improved access to relevant and updated information about the SDGs.

The encyclopedia on the SDGs coordinated by Leal Filho et al. (2020) analysed the importance of ICT skills in achieving SDG 4 (quality education). The authors examined different educational approaches supported by ICT, including the use of digital platforms, open educational resources and online learning tools. Additionally, they included case studies where ICT significantly improved access to education in rural and marginalised communities, demonstrating its potential to reduce educational disparities. Similarly, the systematic review by Carrión-Martínez et al. (2020) on the influence of technological advances in ESD concluded that various educational aspects improve with ICT incorporation, such as access to information, the implementation of more dynamic and innovative methodologies, the promotion of global collaboration among students and educators, and the reduction of educational gaps.

Importance of Including the SDGs in Course Content: Student Perception

A different perspective on the importance of including the SDGs in the curriculum comes from student perception. Ho et al. (2022) conducted a study among university students, finding that they value the integration of the SDGs in their education, which increases their global knowledge and international mobility. Additionally, these authors reported that female participants in the study gave greater importance to the SDGs than males. Similarly, Jones et al. (Jones et al., 2024) combined quantitative and qualitative surveys to evaluate student engagement and perception of the SDGs, concluding that students value the SDGs as useful learning tools, though they express scepticism about their feasibility by 2030. The results also showed significant differences in SDG commitment, leading the authors to suggest the need for specific strategies to engage all students.

Another implication of student perceptions regarding the importance of the SDGs in their academic trajectory is the connection to academic performance. Edgerton and McKechnie (2023) found that a positive academic environment, including SDG integration, significantly improves student engagement and academic performance. The study concluded that students who perceive their institution as concerned with the SDGs develop a more committed attitude and higher academic performance.

In line with the cited authors, studies have also analysed how pedagogical methods influence the effectiveness of the SDGs from the student perspective. Elmassri et al. (2023) noted that while students recognise the importance of the SDGs, they also acknowledge the need for more innovative pedagogical methods for effective and not merely symbolic SDG integration.

However, findings in a different direction have been reported. The study conducted by Kleespies and Dierkes (2022) examined the perception of the SDGs among students from 41 countries involved in the environmental sector. The research, which encompassed a large sample of 4,305 university students, evaluated how each of the 17 SDGs was valued. One key finding of the study is the negative correlation between a country's Human Development Index (HDI) and the importance attributed to the SDGs. The results indicated that in countries with a higher HDI, students considered the SDGs to be less important compared to those in countries with a lower HDI. This suggests that in more developed nations, the perceived urgency regarding the SDGs is lower.

Another study (Mawonde & Togo, 2021) found that university students indicated a lack of interest in practices related to the SDGs, which can be attributed to their disconnection from campus and limited motivation towards sustainable development. According to these authors, students prioritise obtaining a university qualification over learning about sustainability and the SDGs, considering it more important to complete their studies to enter the job market.

Transfer and Application of the SDGs: From Education to Professional and Personal Practice

One aspect to consider in the long term regarding the inclusion of the SDGs in curricula is how students will use them as future professionals after their university education. Sterling (2010) analysed the impact of ESD on acquiring transversal competencies. The results indicate that integrating the SDGs into higher education not only prepares students for future professional challenges but also develops key competencies such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and teamwork. Concerning professional development, there is growing demand for professionals skilled in sustainability, and universities need to adapt their programmes to meet this demand (Lozano et al., 2017). This study on the impact of higher education on sustainable development concluded that universities demonstrating a strong institutional commitment to the SDGs and fostering collaborative networks significantly impact the development sustainability competencies among

their students. Additionally, SDG training not only improves student employability by aligning with labour market demands but also promotes a holistic and multidisciplinary approach to problem-solving (Aleixo et al., 2018).

Studies have also examined conflict resolution capacity in students committed to the SDGs. Picado-Valverde et al. (2022) found that these students develop skills compatible with community activism, suggesting that integrating the SDGs into education better prepares future professionals to face social challenges.

Overall, research has shown that students with greater knowledge of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are more likely to apply this knowledge in the future. Cachero et al. (2023) emphasised the importance of university students understanding and knowing the SDGs, as this better prepares them to implement these goals in their future professional fields. Similarly, Veeran et al. (2024) revealed that students with greater knowledge of the SDGs show increased motivation to apply this knowledge in their future careers. These studies highlight the need to strengthen education on the SDGs to ensure their effective application in the future.

On the other hand, some studies indicate that, although higher education programmes can increase knowledge about the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), this does not always guarantee effective practical application in the future. Kioupi and Voulvoulis (2020) highlighted that despite students acquiring knowledge about the SDGs, there are implementation challenges that may prevent this knowledge from translating into concrete action. Similarly, Buerkle et al. (2023) examined the alignment of higher education teaching with the SDGs and suggest that the practical application of this knowledge is not always guaranteed due to various educational and structural factors. These findings underscore the need to address the barriers limiting the effectiveness of sustainability education to ensure that knowledge of the SDGs translates into meaningful actions in the future.

In this line, Lozano et al. (Lozano et al., 2017) showed an important limitation in integrating sustainability into university curricula: although various pedagogical approaches have been proposed to impart Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), the effective connection between these approaches and the acquisition of sustainability competencies has been scarce. Among the competencies analysed in this study, personal involvement stands out as key, as it reflects not only knowledge and skills in sustainability but also the desire and intention to apply these principles in the future. This work supports the idea that although higher education increases knowledge about the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), their practical implementation requires specific and comprehensive educational approaches that address the necessary competencies for sustainable development, including the personal commitment of students to apply sustainability in their lives and careers (Lozano et al., 2017).

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a quasi-experimental control group design with pre-test and post-test to evaluate the impact of an educational intervention, such as Project-Based Learning (PBL) on the knowledge and perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among university students. This design was selected to preserve the ecological validity of the study, so that the intervention was carried out in natural groups of students. This required balancing the need for rigorous evaluation of the effectiveness of the intervention with the practical considerations of working within existing classroom structures. All participants provided informed consent, and confidentiality and anonymity of the collected data were guaranteed.

Participants

The sample was composed of 199 students (71.9% female) from the first year of the Primary and Early Childhood Education Degrees at the University of Cordoba (Spain). The age of the participants ranged from 18 to 25 years old (87.4% between 18 and 20, $n = 174$; 10.6% between 21 and 23 $n = 21$; 1.5% aged 24 or more years old, $n = 3$). 75.9% of the participants belonged to the Primary Education Degree ($n = 151$), while 24.1% ($n = 48$) were in the Early Childhood Education Degree.

Instruments

The Questionnaire on Knowledge and Perception of the SDGs (Esteller-Cano et al., 2023) was used to measure not only the students' level of knowledge about the SDGs but also their attitudes, including the perceived importance of integrating the SDGs into their education, the convenience of their inclusion in professional training, and the likelihood of applying them in their future personal and professional lives. The instrument consists of a total of 42 items, distributed across three dimensions: (a) Knowledge of the SDGs (18 items): students' information about SDGs is assessed in this dimension. It focuses on measuring how much students knew about the SDGs in general. Responses were given on a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Not at all) to 4 (Extremely), (b) Importance of the SDGs (18 items): it measures students' perceptions of the importance of incorporating the SDGs into the course. Responses were collected using a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Not important at all) to 4 (Very important), (c) Convenience and Transferability of the SDGs (6 items): it analyses students' perceptions of the convenience of including the SDGs in their academic training and their

professional utility. Additionally, it assesses students' views on the applicability of the SDGs and their potential to contribute to these goals in their professional and personal lives. The response scale for the four convenience items was a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Not convenient at all) to 4 (Very convenient). For transferability items, a 4-point Likert scale was used, ranging from 1 (Not at all) to 4 (Extremely).

The internal consistency of the questionnaire was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega. The coefficients reached a large size in all three dimensions: (a) Knowledge of the SDGs: $\alpha = .94$, $\omega = .94$; (b) Importance of the SDGs: $\alpha = .93$, $\omega = .93$; (c) Convenience and Transferability of the SDGs: $\alpha = .86$, $\omega = .85$.

Procedure

Participants were selected through incidental sampling. The questionnaire was administered online along with the informed consent form. Data collection was conducted in selected classrooms, informing participants about the anonymous, confidential and voluntary nature of their participation. The average duration for completing the questionnaire was 10 to 15 minutes, in the presence of the researchers.

The educational intervention aimed to enhance knowledge of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), recognised the importance of incorporating the SDGs into undergraduate courses, and assessed students' perceptions of the implementation of the SDGs in their future professional and personal lives. The design included a control group and an experimental group which consisted of first-year students in Primary Education and Early Childhood Education undergraduate programmes.

The educational intervention implemented in the experimental group was based on the principles of PBL. Students worked on specific projects related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), selecting one of the 17 SDGs so that all SDGs were chosen by at least one team. They investigated it, diagnosed problems and developed creative solutions. The intervention focused on real and relevant issues, such as the 2030 Agenda SDGs, promoting meaningful and contextualised learning. Students worked in teams throughout the process, fostering social and teamwork skills, a fundamental characteristic of PBL. They also created digital resources and presentations to communicate their findings and proposals, consistent with the generation of an end product in PBL. Throughout the intervention, formative assessments and reflections were conducted on the process and learning, allowing for continuous adjustments and improvements. These elements demonstrate how the PBL methodology not only adapts to contemporary educational needs but also drives students to become active agents in their own learning, developing essential competencies to face global challenges.

The intervention was carried out as follows. All students, both in the control group (N=18) and the experimental group (N=181), received training on the SDGs as part of the course content unit where the questionnaires were administered. A traditional methodology was implemented in the control group (i.e., expository teaching). The methodology used in the experimental group, on the other hand, followed PBL-specific stages: students participated in a four-phase structured intervention, each designed to address different aspects of learning and applying the SDGs. In phase 1 –immersion and selection of the SDGs –, students individually searched for information on the 2030 Agenda and the SDGs using resources such as academic articles, official UN documents and multimedia materials. Subsequently, they worked in groups of 4-5 to synthesise the most relevant information and collaboratively chose one SDG to focus on. The professors provided support by reviewing preliminary choices and suggesting ways to deepen their understanding of the selected goal. In phase 2 –critical analysis and diagnosis–, students worked in small groups to analyse the SDG they had selected and identify the social issues hindering its achievement. For instance, one group focused on SDG 13 (Climate Action) and explored how industrial emissions contribute to urban pollution. Using case studies and data from the World Health Organization, they discovered that their city's air quality had been ranked among the lowest in the region. Teachers guided the process with questions like, "What cultural or political factors exacerbate this issue?" and provided tailored feedback to help students refine their arguments. During phase 3 –creation and use of ICT–, students worked in groups of 4-5 to develop digital resources, such as videos or presentations, to raise awareness about their chosen SDG. For instance, one group used Canva to design a presentation on the importance of clean water (SDG 6), blending striking visuals with compelling data from UNICEF reports. To ensure effective collaboration, group members divided responsibilities into content creation, design, and editing. Teachers supported the process by recommending tools, helping students manage their workloads, and guiding them in building strong teamwork dynamics. Finally, phase 4 –communication and dissemination– involved project presentation activities and social media publication. The students presented their projects in various formats, such as oral presentations, written reports, and videos. To extend their impact beyond the academic environment, they shared their contributions on social media platforms such as Instagram and Twitter, aiming to connect with a wider audience. In this regard, the teachers highlighted that this experience helped develop collaborative skills and improved digital competence.

Regarding evaluation, both groups –control and experimental– completed the Questionnaire on Knowledge and Perception of the SDGs at the beginning (pre-test) and the end (post-test) of the study period. This allowed for an assessment of the intervention's impact, providing comparative data to test progress in SDG knowledge and perception among students in the experimental group.

Data Analysis

Firstly, we explored the initial position of the sample (pretest) in the three dependent variables, discriminating by gender. Likewise, we ascertained whether the two groups in the sample belonged to the same population, ruling out the existence of significant differences by t-tests. Subsequently, we implemented a correlational analysis of the score distributions of the three dependent variables.

After the preliminary analyses, we moved on to critical analysis that allowed us to test the hypothesis. Specifically, we conducted a repeated-measures ANOVA to determine the interaction between the between-subjects factor (group) and the within-subjects factor (test or time) and thereby ascertain whether the two groups had evolved differently between both measurement moments. Data were coded and analysed using the SPSS version 28 software.

Results

Preliminary Analyses: Descriptive Statistics and Exploration of Initial Gender and Group Differences

Regarding data collected in the pretest, the highest mean score observed on the SDG scale corresponded to the dimension of the convenience of using the SDGs in subjects ($M = 3.14$; $SD = 0.45$), followed by the importance of introducing the SDGs into the curriculum ($M = 3.11$; $SD = 0.46$) and the level of knowledge of the SDGs ($M = 1.82$; $SD = 0.48$). The correlation analysis of the variables indicated a positive association between the importance of the SDGs and the convenience of using them for professional development and transfer to personal and professional life, as well as between this convenience and knowledge about SDGs (see Table 1).

Table 1. Means and Standard Deviations by Gender, and Pearson's Product-Moment Correlations Between the Three Dependent Variables in the Pre-Test.

Variables	M			SD			1	2	3
	Male (N = 56)	Female (N = 143)	Total (N = 199)	Male (N = 56)	Female (N = 143)	Total (N = 199)			
1. Knowledge	1.80	1.82	1.82	0.45	0.49	0.48	-		
2. Importance	2.94	3.18	3.11	0.52	0.42	0.46	.056	-	
3. Convenience	3.05	3.17	3.14	0.49	0.43	0.45	.184**	.564**	-

Note: ** $p < .01$

Adopting a gender perspective, the existence of significant differences between male and female students in the pre-test was tested, identifying higher means among women in the dimension of importance ($t [197] = -3.35$, $p < .001$, $d = -0.528$; $M_{\text{male}} = 2.94$, $M_{\text{female}} = 3.18$). As for the dimension of convenience, no statistically significant difference was found, although the p -value was close to the conventional threshold ($t [197] = -1.77$, $p = .078$, $d = -0.279$; $M_{\text{male}} = 3.05$, $M_{\text{female}} = 3.17$).

Since the subjects were not randomly assigned to the groups, the means of the experimental and control groups in the pretest were also compared to confirm that both came from the same population. Results showed that the two groups did not differ in any of the three dependent variables: Knowledge ($t [197] = -0.96$, $p = .336$); importance ($t [197] = 0.18$, $p = .856$); and convenience ($t [197] = 1.22$, $p = .224$).

Critical Analysis: Effectiveness of the Intervention

To test the hypothesis on the effectiveness of the educational intervention strategy (PBL methodology), we conducted repeated measures one-way ANOVA with condition or group as the between-subjects factor (experimental – control) and time (pre – post-test) as the within-subjects factor (i.e., a 2 x 2 design). We found a significant effect of time x group on the dimension of knowledge about SDGs ($F (1,197) = 7.71$, $p = .006$, $\eta^2 = .038$). Specifically, participants who learned about SDGs with a PBL methodology developed significantly greater knowledge than participants in the control group ($\Delta M_{\text{exp}} = 1.10$ vs $\Delta M_{\text{con}} = 0.67$) (see Table 2).

The interaction effect was not verified as regards the importance of integrating the SDGs into the curriculum or their relevance for future professional and personal lives ($p > .05$). Interestingly, however, both groups made significant progress between the pre-test and post-test in the dimension of convenience (Experimental: $t [180] = -5.49$, $p < .001$, $d = -0.408$; Control: $t [17] = -2.33$, $p = .032$, $d = -0.550$). Regarding the dimension of importance, the evolution was clearly positive in the experimental group ($t [180] = -5.33$, $p < .001$, $d = -0.396$) and marginally significant in the control condition ($t [17] = -1.79$, $p = .090$, $d = -0.423$).

Table 2. Means and Standard Deviations for Between-Subjects (Group) and Within-Subjects (Time) Factors, and F-Test for the Interaction Effect of Time × Group

Variables	M				SD				df	F	p	η ²
	Experimental (N = 181)		Control (N = 18)		Experimental (N = 181)		Control (N = 18)					
Group	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post				
1. Knowledge	1.81	2.91	1.92	2.59	0.48	0.45	0.45	0.47	1, 197	7.71	.006	.038
2. Importance	3.11	3.32	3.09	3.36	0.47	0.51	0.43	0.48	1, 197	0.20	.654	.001
3. Convenience	3.15	3.34	3.02	3.36	0.45	0.44	0.44	0.42	1, 197	1.79	.182	.009

Figure 1 shows the interaction confirmed by ANOVA, highlighting the distance between the two groups in the post-test in favour of the experimental condition. This difference reached statistical significance, with the effect size being assessed as moderate ($t [197] = 2.85, p = .005, d = 0.704; M_{exp} = 2.91, M_{con} = 2.59$). The figure also shows the positive evolution of both groups between the two measurement moments, with higher means over time in both the experimental ($t [180] = -23.52, p < .001, d = -1.748; M_{pre} = 1.81, M_{post} = 2.91$) and control group ($t [17] = -4.23, p < .001, d = -0.996; M_{pre} = 1.92, M_{post} = 2.59$). However, the significant effect due to interaction confirms that the PBL methodology was more effective than traditional instruction.

Figure 1. Means, Standard, Deviations, Between-Subjects, Group, Within-Subjects, Time, Factors, F-Test, Interaction, Effect, Time, Group

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of PBL-based educational intervention on university students' knowledge and perceptions of the SDGs. The results confirm that the intervention showed a good level of effectiveness in this regard. Specifically, PBL was more effective than a traditional methodology in improving students' knowledge. However, PBL did not drive the perceived importance of integrating the SDGs into the curriculum or their relevance for future professional and personal lives to a greater extent than a traditional teaching approach. Even so, the effectiveness of the PBL methodology is valued because it was able to improve the dimension in which participants initially scored lower (i.e., they had very limited knowledge about the SDGs). Because their assessment of the importance, desirability, and transferability of the SDGs was already initially high, it was difficult to increase it significantly more than through other strategies.

The significant improvement in students' knowledge of the SDGs aligns with previous studies highlighting the effectiveness of PBL in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes (Balleisen et al., 2024). The increase in knowledge can be attributed to the active, student-centred nature of PBL, which encourages deeper exploration and understanding of complex topics like the SDGs (Arisetiyana et al., 2020). Moreover, previous studies have demonstrated that PBL methodologies can enhance understanding of the SDGs while engaging students. This participatory approach could increase the capacity to improve students' understanding and commitment to the SDGs. Additionally, collaborative learning accompanied by an interdisciplinary approach helps students comprehend the interconnectedness of sustainability issues while promoting the development of critical and reflective skills (Carrión-Martínez et al., 2020; Olojo, 2021).

Regarding the other two dimensions of the study, the findings indicated a parallel evolution in the experimental and control groups in their assessment of the importance and relevance of applying the SDGs in the future. This suggests that, while knowledge can be effectively improved through such intervention, the other two dimensions may require more intensive or different types of interventions. However, the objective of improving the methodology is not as important in these dimensions, both because of the strong initial assessment and because of the fact, as evidenced in our study, that a traditional methodology could be enough to further increase the average scores in importance, convenience and transfer of the SDGs.

Perhaps the assessment of university students in dimensions such as the importance attributed to the SDGs cannot be increased further in some contexts. In fact, the study conducted by Kleespies and Dierkes (Kleespies & Dierkes, 2022), which examined the perception of the SDGs among university students from 41 countries, found a negative correlation between a country's Human Development Index (HDI) and the importance attributed to the SDGs. It was found that in countries with a higher HDI, students considered the SDGs less important compared to those in countries with a lower HDI. This result suggests that in countries that score very high in the HDI ranking published by the United Nations Development Programme (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2024), the perceived urgency regarding the SDGs is lower.

HDI is not the only factor associated with the importance attributed to the SDGs by university students. In fact, the Spanish sample in our study scored high on the importance given to SDGs while Spain occupies a high position in the HDI ranking of the United Nations. For their part, Mawonde and Togo (2021) report a lack of interest of students from a South African university in practices related to the SDGs. According to these authors, students prioritise obtaining a university qualification over learning about sustainability and the SDGs, considering it more important to complete their studies to enter the job market. These types of results go beyond the HDI as a conditioning variable and suggest other categories of factors that influence perceptions about social, economic, and environmental sustainability. For instance, a sustainable university can influence students to engage in SDG-related practices if it leads by example (Leal Filho et al., 2019). An integrated sustainability approach, with a firm commitment to institutional action that involves all stakeholders, could stimulate students' interest and understanding of the SDGs. This type of evidence underscores the importance of adapting educational strategies to the contextual factors of students to increase the value and support for the SDGs. At the same time, it highlights the need to develop institutional policies in which training actions should be adequately framed.

In the case of the third dimension –convenience and transferability of the SDGs–, the fact that the PBL methodology did not prove to be substantially more effective than the traditional teaching methodology might be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the transition from knowledge acquisition to practical application is complex and multifaceted. Sterling et al. (2013) noted that while integrating the SDGs into higher education prepares students for future professional challenges, it also requires the development of key competencies such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and teamwork. It is possible that the present intervention did not fully address these competencies, thereby limiting its impact on students' improvement in terms of the perceived relevance of the SDGs in their future lives.

Furthermore, although higher education programmes can increase knowledge about the SDGs, this does not always guarantee effective practical application. Kioupi and Voulvoulis (2020) highlighted that despite students acquiring knowledge about the SDGs, there are implementation challenges that may prevent this knowledge from translating into concrete action. Educational and structural barriers, such as a lack of practical training and real-world application opportunities, could hinder the translation of SDG knowledge into meaningful actions (Buerkle et al., 2023). Additionally, Lozano et al. (2017) pointed out that the effective connection between educational approaches and the acquisition of sustainability competencies has been scarce. Personal involvement is a critical competency that reflects not only knowledge and skills in sustainability but also the desire and intention to apply these principles in the future. The intervention in our study may not have sufficiently fostered this personal commitment, advancing only slightly the perceived convenience of applying the SDGs in future professional and personal contexts.

Another finding of the study relates to gender. Both before and after the intervention, significant differences were observed between men and women regarding the importance of introducing the SDGs into the curriculum, with women showing higher scores. There was also a marginally significant difference in the dimension of convenience and transfer in favour of female students. These results highlight the need to consider gender perspectives when designing and implementing educational interventions related to the SDGs. The greater importance and perceived convenience among

women suggest that female students may be more receptive to sustainability education, which could be leveraged to enhance overall student engagement with the SDGs (Ho et al., 2022).

Regarding the implications for educational practice, it is important to analyse the ingredients of the PBL methodology that could have contributed to the experimental group distancing itself from the control group in their knowledge of the SDGs. Firstly, one key factor might have been the integration of activities requiring the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) within the PBL framework. The United Nations has highlighted the importance of investing in ICT access and quality education to promote lasting peace, as these tools enhance access to relevant and up-to-date information about the SDGs, facilitating dynamic and interactive learning that fosters innovative methodologies, increased student engagement and deeper understanding of the SDGs (Leal Filho et al., 2020; Olojo, 2021). Secondly, another component is an interdisciplinary and collaborative approach. Students were encouraged to analyze the selected SDG from social, environmental, and technological perspectives. Working in small groups, they took on specific roles such as researcher, designer, or coordinator. For example, one group focused on SDG 4 (Quality Education) and designed an interactive presentation on educational disparities in rural areas. This collaborative approach not only fostered dynamic discussions but also helped students connect the interdisciplinary dimensions of the SDGs with real-world challenges, providing them with a deeper understanding of global issues. It can help students better understand the interconnectedness of sustainability issues, promoting the development of critical and reflective skills (Carrión-Martínez et al., 2020; Olojo, 2021).

To sum up, this study suggests that integrating SDGs into higher education curricula through active learning methodologies such as PBL can better prepare students for future challenges by deepening their understanding of the SDGs. As detailed in the methodology section, the implementation of PBL followed a structured four-phase approach (immersion, analysis, creation, and dissemination), ensuring its alignment with the study's objectives and the development of key competencies related to the SDGs. However, additional or complementary educational strategies may be needed to better address the perceived importance and relevance of the SDGs, ensuring a comprehensive preparation of students to face sustainability challenges in their professional and personal lives.

Regarding the limitations of the study, it is important to note that the sample was limited to a single university and education degree. This factor may restrict the generalizability of the results to other institutions and educational contexts. Additionally, it would be beneficial to apply a more prolonged intervention and observe the changes over the long term to better understand the sustainability of the effects. Another potential limitation is the use of self-report instruments, which can introduce bias due to social desirability. Future studies should consider incorporating objective measures and expanding the sample to include multiple institutions to enhance the robustness and applicability of the findings.

Conclusion

This study evaluated the impact of an educational intervention using Project-Based Learning (PBL) on university students' knowledge and perceptions of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The results demonstrated a significant improvement in students' knowledge of the SDGs when using PBL over the progress made through a traditional methodology, but this did not happen with the perceived importance or relevance of integrating the SDGs into future professional and personal lives. Additionally, significant gender differences were observed, with female students consistently rating the importance – and perhaps convenience – of the SDGs higher than their male counterparts. These findings indicate that while PBL effectively enhances knowledge over traditional teaching strategies, additional or different educational strategies may be required to influence other dimensions of commitment to the SDGs more effectively. The use of ICT within the PBL methodology was a key element for students not only to deepen their knowledge of the SDGs but also to feel more engaged with the proposed activities. During the different phases of the project, these tools played a fundamental role. For instance, they facilitated research on the 2030 Agenda, enabled the creation of materials such as videos and presentations, and helped share the results through social media, thereby extending their reach.

This study offers new insights into the application of PBL in higher education, highlighting its effectiveness in enhancing students' understanding of the SDGs. However, it also uncovers limitations, particularly in fostering perceptions of the importance and relevance of the SDGs. As a result, more holistic and complementary methodologies are proposed for integration with PBL, such as service-learning (SL) or structured debates. Future research could examine the impact of combining these methodologies on the development of critical thinking and the practical application of acquired knowledge in real-world contexts. This potential is further explored in the recommendations section.

Recommendations

We recommend that future researchers and professionals combine PBL with other educational methodologies that strengthen key competencies such as critical thinking, problem-solving and collaboration. This recommendation is based on the findings of this study, which revealed that while PBL has proven effective in improving students' knowledge of the SDGs, it had a limited impact on influencing their perceptions of the importance and relevance of these goals in their personal and professional lives.

For instance, the combination of SL with PBL has been shown to be effective in developing transversal competencies such as civic responsibility, communication, and reflective thinking in the context of higher music education (Cuervo-Calvo & Cabedo-Mas, 2024). Furthermore, structured debates have been identified as an effective methodology for fostering critical thinking, teamwork, and student motivation, making them a valuable complement to PBL (Vásquez González et al., 2017). These methodologies can address the limitations of PBL by encouraging deeper personal reflection and direct engagement with real-world challenges, thereby strengthening the overall impact of educational interventions related to the SDGs.

Moreover, it is essential to adapt educational interventions to the socioeconomic contexts of students, considering factors like the HDI, which can influence perceptions of the SDGs. Future studies should design strategies that respond to local conditions and promote greater relevance and commitment to sustainability goals in different contexts.

Finally, for knowledge about the SDGs to translate into concrete actions, it is crucial to foster students' personal commitment through practical application in real-world projects. The integration of ICT and an interdisciplinary approach in educational interventions can help students better understand the complexity of sustainability challenges, encouraging more active and meaningful participation.

Limitations

This study, while offering valuable insights into the impact of PBL on university students' knowledge and perceptions of the SDGs, presents a number of limitations that should be considered. Firstly, the sample size and scope were limited to students from a single university, specifically within the Primary and Early Childhood Education degrees. This restricts the ability to generalize the findings to other academic programs or institutions. Future research should include a wider diversity of educational contexts and degree programs to determine if the effects observed are consistent across different settings.

Secondly, the duration of the intervention was relatively short, which may have influenced the depth of the impact, particularly regarding students' perceptions of the importance and relevance of the SDGs. A longer intervention could allow for more sustained engagement and a deeper impact on students' attitudes. Extending the study period would provide additional insights into the long-term sustainability of the changes observed in knowledge and perceptions.

Finally, the study relied primarily on self-report instruments to measure the dependent variables, which may have introduced biases such as social desirability bias in the results. Although the internal consistency of the instruments was strong, the reliance on subjective measures limits the ability to fully assess participants' true understanding and commitment to the SDGs.

Addressing these limitations will allow future studies to improve the robustness and applicability of their findings, offering more detailed and transferable conclusions about the effectiveness of PBL and other pedagogical approaches in promoting sustainability education in higher education.

Ethics Statements

All participants provided informed consent, and confidentiality and anonymity of the collected data were guaranteed. Data collected had no relevance to the identity of the participants, were not subject to data protection, and were not affected by social desirability.

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Conflict of Interest

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Espino-Díaz: Conceptualization, design, analysis, writing, editing/reviewing and supervision. Luque-González: Conceptualization, design, analysis, writing, editing/reviewing and supervision. Fernández-Camínero: Conceptualization, design, analysis, writing, editing/reviewing and supervision. Álvarez-Castillo: Conceptualization, design, analysis, writing, editing/reviewing and supervision.

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